

Effects of nitrogen-purging and heat treatment on the tensile performance of 3D-printed continuous fiber-reinforced composites

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Background

Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) --- Depositing the extruded materials into a 3D structure layer by layer through heated nozzles using **thermoplastic** and **fiber** filaments.

Schematic diagram of FDM printing [1]

Moisture content

ULTEM 9085

- <0.1% moisture: smooth, consolidated fracture surface
- ~0.16% moisture: onset of voids, reduced strength and strain
- >0.4% moisture: high porosity, void-rich specimens

(Zaldivar et al., *Addit. Manuf.*, 2018)

Post-annealing

CCF/PEEK

- Improved crystallinity, interfacial bonding, infiltration and diffusion among adjacent filaments and layers
- Optimal treatment: 250°C and 6h
- Tensile strength and interlaminar shear strength increased by 85% and 15%, respectively

(Wang & Zou, *Coatings*, 2022)

Materials, printer & specimen configurations

Materials

Matrix

Onyx (micro carbon fiber filled nylon)

Continuous
fiber
filaments

Carbon Fiber (CFF)
Glass Fiber (GFF)
Kevlar Fiber (KFF)

Specimen configurations

Geometry

Fiber pattern
Isotropic (0°)

Onyx raster angle
(±45°)

Stacking sequence

Printer: Markforged® Mark Two Generation II

Dry box for
Onyx spool
storage

Printing head

Printing bed

Hydrometer

Fiber filament
spool

Specimen processing

Nitrogen (N ₂)-purging		Post-annealing		Scenario	Annotation
Duration	Throughout the printing process	Temperature (°C)	90, 120, 150, 180	As-printed (untreated)	AP
Gas condition	Pure and dry gas at room temperature	Duration (hr)	2	Fan oven annealed at 90°C	FO_90
Average RH without N ₂ -purging (%)	27.9	Annealing condition	Fan-circulating with environmental air	Fan oven annealed at 150°C	FO_150
Average RH with N ₂ -purging (%)	6.4	Cooling condition	Rapid removal and cooling at room temperature	Fan oven annealed at 180°C	FO_180
				Nitrogen-purged	N ₂
				Nitrogen-purged and then annealed at 150°C	N ₂ +FO_150

Note: RH refers to relative humidity.

Experimental set-up

MTS Model 43 machine (50kN)

Video extensometer

Tensile specimen

GFF/Onyx specimens in quasi-static tensile testing

GFF/Onyx_AP test recording

GFF/Onyx_FO150 test recording

Results

Stress-strain curves of N₂-purged specimens

Ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of post-annealed specimens

Results

Ashby diagram of the tensile properties of CFRCs

➤ The UTS of GFF/Onyx after the combined treatment reached 420 MPa, which falls into the upper range of UTS values of industrial aluminum alloys (2000 series).

Results – Deformation mechanisms

Results – SEM analysis

Onyx and CFF/Onyx interlayer side-views

Magnified side-views

Thermal expansion of CFF/Onyx and KFF/Onyx at 180°C

Results – DSC and XRD analyses

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

X-ray diffraction (XRD)

- DSC shows structural relaxation and increased stability in post-annealed specimens;
- Post-annealed specimens display lower moisture content;
- XRD identifies the polyamide component in Onyx filaments as PA6;
- Both DSC and XRD confirm higher crystallinity after post-annealing.

The response of CFRCs to N₂-purging and post-annealing was material-dependent, emphasizing the need for a targeted approach in optimizing the mechanical properties of 3D-printed composite materials.

- **KFF/Onyx:** N₂-purging, post-annealing, and combined treatment (N₂+FO150) improved both Young's modulus and UTS.
- **GFF/Onyx:** N₂-purging, post-annealing, and combined treatment (N₂+FO150) had minor effects on Young's modulus ($\leq 6\%$) but significantly enhanced UTS, reaching 399 MPa with combined treatment – comparable to 2000 series aluminum, showing potential for aerospace applications.
- **CFF/Onyx:** N₂-purging improved Young's modulus; however, post-annealing and combined treatments decreased UTS due to defects such as interlayer gaps, thermal expansion and carbon fiber embrittlement.

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Thank you!

Strategies for further enhancement of 3D-printed CFRCs

